

Data Governance Plan for Mozambique - Energy Access and Modelling

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Executive Summary

Mozambique is advancing towards universal energy access by 2030 by constructing an integrated planning platform. This initiative involves key actors, including the Ministry of Mineral Resources and Energy, grid and off-grid operators, the private sector, the Energy Regulatory Authority, and financiers. To streamline efforts, it is essential to define and communicate the roles of each stakeholder. This will prevent duplicative actions, enhance transparency, and ensure coordinated progress in electrification, fostering collaboration and efficiency in achieving the nation's energy goals.

Recommendations

1. **Role clarification and communication:** Clearly define and communicate the responsibilities of each stakeholder, ensuring all parties understand their contributions to the national electrification goals.
2. **Centralized data sharing:** Establish a centralized data-sharing mechanism within the platform, accessible to all stakeholders, to avoid duplication of efforts and promote informed decision-making.

3. **Regular coordination meetings:** Facilitate regular coordination meetings among stakeholders to review progress, address challenges, and adjust strategies as needed.
4. **Transparency and accountability:** Implement transparent reporting and monitoring systems to track progress and ensure accountability across all involved entities.
5. **Capacity building:** Provide training and support to stakeholders, especially at local levels, to enhance their capacity to contribute effectively to the electrification initiative.
6. **Engage private sector and financiers:** Actively involve the private sector and financial institutions in the planning and execution phases to leverage investment in achieving energy access targets.

1. Introduction

Purpose: Mozambique is currently constructing an integrated planning platform to make a structured contribution to the attainment of universal access to energy by 2030.

Given the multiplicity of actors involved in the sector, including the Ministry of Mineral Resources and Energy, entities operating on and off the grid, the private sector, the Energy Regulatory Authority, and financiers, it is crucial to define the role of each actor and disseminate this information to prevent the replication of actions and demonstrate transparency in the electrification process.

Objective:

The main objectives of this data governance plan are:

- **Ensure data accuracy:** Maintain the integrity and reliability of geospatial and energy data to support accurate decision-making.
- **Enhance data accessibility:** Facilitate easy access to data for all stakeholders, including government agencies, NGOs, and the private sector.
- **Strengthen data security:** Protect sensitive data from unauthorized access and breaches, ensuring compliance with local and international data protection standards.

Scope:

This plan covers all geospatial and energy data collected, processed, and used by stakeholders involved in energy access initiatives in Mozambique. This includes data from various sources such as satellite imagery, survey data, infrastructure data, energy consumption patterns, and demographic information.

2. Methodology**Modelling Approach/Tool Implemented****Data Collection:**

Data collection will be conducted using GPS-enabled mobile devices during field surveys in rural areas, ensuring precise location-based information. For remote and less accessible regions, high-resolution satellite imagery from Sentinel-2 and drones will complement the field data, providing comprehensive coverage. This dual approach ensures that data is both precise and complete, allowing for effective analysis and planning in support of Mozambique's universal energy access initiative.

Collection Methods:

- Field Surveys
- Remote Sensing
- Crowdsourcing

Data Storage:

Will be implemented secure, scalable storage solutions that include redundancy measures to ensure data integrity and prevent loss. These solutions should be capable of handling large datasets, such as geospatial data from field surveys and satellite imagery while providing robust protection against unauthorized access and potential failures. Regular backups and cloud-based options should be considered.

Data archiving and disposal:

Developed comprehensive guidelines for systematically archiving valuable data, ensuring it remains accessible and secure for future reference. Establish clear protocols

for the secure disposal of outdated, including methods for permanently deleting or anonymizing sensitive information. These guidelines should adhere to best practices in data management, comply with legal and regulatory requirements, and incorporate periodic reviews to ensure continued relevance and security in data retention and disposal processes.

Data cleaning and formatting:

Data will undergo a comprehensive multi-step cleaning process to ensure accuracy and consistency which includes Outlier Detection, Standardization of Units, and Validation, this process ensures the data's integrity and suitability for further analysis.

Data Sources:

Primary data will be sourced from Institutions such as the Ministry of Education and Health, the Ministry of Agriculture, National Institute of Statistics among others. Field surveys will be conducted by a multidisciplinary team involving the above-mentioned bodies, while secondary data will be obtained from the international energy datasets.

- **Primary Data:** From Public and Energy Institutions and Data collected directly through field surveys.
- **Secondary Data:** Data obtained from third-party sources such as academic research, or international organizations.
- **Open Data Platforms:** Publicly available data sources, such as OpenStreetMap, World Bank datasets, VIDA datasets, and Geospatial Development Agency (ADE) data portals.

Assumptions:

Data Quality

The process begins with rigorous **Data Accuracy** measures, where data undergoes validation and verification before entry into the database, with an accuracy standard of 90%. This ensures that every attribute is correctly placed and recorded.

To maintain **Data Consistency**, standardized formats, definitions, and metadata are applied, ensuring uniformity across different datasets. Attributes are verified against predefined standards to avoid discrepancies.

A **Data Completeness** plan guides the collection process, ensuring that all relevant aspects of energy access are thoroughly documented. This plan identifies existing data and gaps, guaranteeing that no crucial information is missed.

Data Timeliness is prioritized by regularly updating data to reflect the current conditions and needs. This ensures that all stakeholders have access to the most recent and relevant information, facilitating effective planning and implementation of energy initiatives.

Data Accessibility

Data Sharing Policy will ensure seamless collaboration among stakeholders while maintaining security. The results of data collection and analysis will be shared via an online platform, where stakeholders will have designated access some with the ability to edit, and others only to view.

Data Access Levels will be carefully defined, with sensitive data restricted to authorized personnel based on their roles. To ensure Data Availability, robust storage solutions with backup and recovery mechanisms will be implemented, guaranteeing continuous access to critical information.

Data Security

Data Protection measures will include encryption, stringent access controls, and continuous monitoring to shield sensitive information from unauthorized access and breaches.

In parallel, the initiative will ensure **Compliance** with both local data protection laws and international standards, maintaining the highest ethical and legal standards.

To prepare for potential threats, a comprehensive **Incident Management** plan will be developed, detailing procedures for responding swiftly and effectively to data breaches or security incidents, minimizing impact, and ensuring swift recovery.

3. Results

The diagram was developed to assess electrification initiatives/projects existing in the country, mapping existing programs and funding, beneficiaries of these projects, and the average consumption of the beneficiaries to illustrate the government's intervention to accelerate the achievement of electrification targets.

The diagram comprises the following entities:

Infrastructure - The name and type of the installed infrastructures with corresponding capacity.

Demographics - for making informed decisions about where and how to electrify a province or district ensuring that the infrastructure meets the needs of the population.

Beneficiaries - detailed data on beneficiary location, type, and average consumption to allow precise planning and more efficient resource use.

Project infrastructure - The infrastructure will be organized by project name with a unique identifier to help track and manage multiple projects within a larger electrification program that is being implemented in the country.

Location - Identifying electrical infrastructures by latitude and longitude to provide precise geographic information, which is critical for planning, tracking, and managing infrastructure development.

4. Discussion

Roles and Responsibilities:

- Data Governance Committee
- **Composition:** Representatives from government bodies (e.g., Ministry of Mineral Resources and Energy, National Institute of Statistics), development partners, NGOs, and private sector entities involved in energy access projects.

Member	Planning Unit	Power Utility	Energy Fund	Geospatial Development Agency	Responsibilities
Roles					
Data Stewards	Admin				<p>Overall responsibility for data governance and strategy implementation.</p> <p>Ensures alignment of data management with organizational goals (ensure data accuracy, consistency, and proper documentation).</p> <p>Facilitate data sharing and coordinate with data users.</p>
Data Owners		Strategy and Business Performance Department	Planning Department		<p>Departmental heads or senior officials who have ultimate authority over specific datasets.</p> <p>Data collection and update</p>
Data Custodians				GIS Department	<p>Technical management of data, including storage,</p> <p>Security, and backup</p>
Data users	All, including the Public and Private sector				Utilize the data for analysis, reporting, and decision-making.

Working Groups:

A Data Governance Working Group will be established, comprising representatives from the Ministry of Mineral Resources and Energy, Planning Unit, Power Utility, Energy Fund, Private Sector and Geospatial Development Agency. This group was formed based on the role that each of the institutions has in the country's electrification process.

The Ministry, which will communicate with all members of the working group and publish the results, will have the main responsibility.

All sensitive data will be encrypted using AES-256, one of the most secure encryption standards available. Access will be tightly controlled through role-based permissions, ensuring that users only access data pertinent to their role. Additionally, regular audits will be conducted to monitor access patterns, detect any anomalies, and ensure compliance with security policies. This combination of encryption, controlled access, and proactive auditing will safeguard the integrity and confidentiality of the data, protecting it from unauthorized access and potential breaches.

5. Conclusion

Geospatial data management is a critical component of successful infrastructure projects, particularly in the electrification process. By ensuring accuracy, integrating data sets, utilizing GIS tools effectively, and maintaining clear communication with stakeholders, projects can be executed more efficiently and with greater positive impact. On the lessons learned we would like to highlight the importance of having accuracy in data collection and the use of reliable sources and accurate methods for collecting and validating geographic information, integration with Other DataSets to provide a comprehensive view of the project, regular updates and share of geospatial data is also important for visualizations as new geospatial data becomes available.

It is important to invest in increasing the technical capabilities by implementing comprehensive training programs for all staff and stakeholders involved in geospatial data management. This should include hands-on training with GIS tools and workshops on integrating geospatial data with other datasets where best practices, lessons learned, and innovative approaches to geospatial data management can be shared across developers and project implementers in our country.

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